

Elastic and Plastic Sections Properties and Buckling Columns in Euler Equation

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1 Elastic and plastic sections

1 Introduction

To study the properties for these sections we can take example like rectangular shape I beam, or W sec. wide flanged section see if there are several different names for them in Iraq . we typically refer to these as a wide flanged section or a W section . Now W section has a symmetric a w symmetric shape , we have flange and web and another flange show in figure 1 a [1][2]and we know from our studies and somewhat intuitively that the neutral axis right in the middle or double symmetry and we can say that this is at location y in figure 1

Figure 1 a

b

c

Figure 2

If we are to apply a moment to this section[3], we end up with a strain and using the assumption that plane strains remain plane which is a very valid assumption especially for flexural bending there like this we end up with a strain distribution in figure 1 b that has a strain at the top which is less than or equal to yield

strain if we remain elastic and a strain at the bottom which is also less than or equal to yield strain and if we now go and look at our material property have in figure 2 [4][5] we have strain and stress if we have an elastic perfect plastic behavior we can get a yield stress and a yield strain we are saying that the strain everywhere is in this linear region this would result in us having a stress distribution that would also be linear and we have episode stress at the top is less than or equal to F_y and stress at the bottom is less than or equal to F_y in figure 1 c , so we have :

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} -\text{linear strain} \\ -\text{linear stress} \end{array} \right\} \text{elastic}$$

We say before that we can jump through this elastic section stuff pretty quickly by instead of going through first principles where we calculate forces within our flange in a weapon and use moment equilibrium and forces we can instead jump to the heat equation where we know that stress is equal to :

$$\sigma = \frac{M y}{I} \rightarrow M = \frac{\sigma I}{y}$$

And we also did define so how do we calculate I for this thing , well there is a number of different approaches to this but since we know we have all the symmetry happening and it arrives is right in the middle there [1]. it's pretty easy to calculate the moment of inertia of the rectangular block and then subtract from it the moment of inertia of the two sections that aren't there between the web and the flanges in other words we can take :

$$I = \frac{1}{12} [bd^3 - (b - w)(d - 2f)^3]$$

So have you can see that we are taking a rectangle entire thing rectangle comprised of the two sides and since they both share the same neutral axis we don't need to apply parallel axis there and if we were to compute this out we would end up with the ability to directly calculate our section modulus for this shape it's a bit easier for us to look at this as an example that we get to in the next step[6] . So, before we do that at this point, we are able to now we can find section modulus let's call that moment of inertia of SX so we can find that find moment yield :

$$M_y = F_y S_x$$

That well it's just a matter of doing the computation by plugging in some values at this point .

1.1 Plastic shape properties

The plastic neutral axis will be at the same location as the elastic neutral axis which is right in the middle so y is equal to $d/2$ and if we were to apply a moment to this thing shown in figure 3 a now let's apply plastic moment M_P and draw our stress distribution and strain distribution will circumscribe strain in figure 2 b we would get an epsilon at the top and now epsilon strain at the bottom its much greater than yield strength . The point that effectively everywhere in the section has plasticized now recall we have a stress strain distribution shown in figure 4 that we consider elastic perfect plastic in other words we have this elastic goes up to epsilon y and then it follows a plastic plateau indefinitely and if that's the case if the strain is much much larger way over off in infinity region shown in figure 2 c[1] , we end up with this plastic stress box to rectangular stress box with magnitudes F_y on top and bottom .

Figure 4

So we know that to be the plastic stress and plastic strain distribution lets zoom in a little bit on the stress block itself and if we come down here and look at it shown in figure 5 , we can see that we are at magnitude F_y in both locations we have this moment we have a height of y and we have force in top flange (F_{ft}) and we have a force in the top web (F_{wt}) and a force in the flange bottom and a force in the web at the bottom

Figure 5

and we know the magnitude of the top flange is going to be the area of the flange shown in figure 2 d multiplied by the stress so it's going to be :

$$F_{ft} = (btf)(F_y)$$

$$F_{fb} = (btf)(F_y)$$

$$F_{wt} = \left[\frac{(d - 2tf)}{2} w \right] F_y$$

$$F_{wb} = \left[\frac{(d - 2tf)}{2} w \right] F_y$$

So now we can solve for the value of the plastic moment by taking the sum of moments about this neutral axis location we call that plastic neutral axis we take the sum of moments through the plastic neutral axis[6]

$$\sum M_{pna} = 0$$

We had end up with M_p and I drew it as going this way is equal :

$$M_p = F_{ft} Y_{ft} + F_{wt} Y_{wt} + F_{fb} Y_{fb} + F_{wb} Y_{wb}$$

That we just determined that the web at bottom and what top forces are the same and the flange bottom and flange top forces are the same we could say :

$$F_{ft} = F_{fb} \quad ; \quad F_{wt} = F_{wb}$$

$$M_p = 2F_{ft} Y_{ft} + 2F_{wt} Y_{wt}$$

$$y_{ft} = \frac{d}{2} - \frac{t_f}{2}$$

$$y_{wt} = \frac{\frac{d}{2} - t_f}{2}$$

lets define : $M_p = F_y Z_x$

plastic section modulus : $Z_x = \frac{M_p}{F_y}$

$K = \text{shape factor} = \frac{Z}{S}$

We know our moment we can back calculate our section modulus and our plastic section modulus and compare it with our elastic modulus but to do that lets look at an example let's put some numbers behind this .

Example 1

$T_f = 20 \text{ mm} ; F_y = 350 \text{ mpa}$

$W = 10 \text{ mm}$

$B = 200 \text{ mm}$

$D = 400 \text{ mm} \quad ; \quad \text{find } M_y , S_x , M_p , Z_x , \text{ shape factor } K$

Sol//

$$I_x = \frac{1}{12} [bd^3 - (b-w)(d-2tf)^3] = \frac{1}{12} [200(300)^3 - (200-10)(400-2(20))^3]$$

$$= 327.95 \times 10^6 \text{ mm}^4$$

$$S_x = I_x / y = 1639.7 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$M_y = F_y S_x = 573.9 \times 10^6 \text{ N.mm}$$

$$F_f = (A_f) F_y = F_y (T_f b) = 350 (20 \times 200) = 1400 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$$

$$F_w = \left(\frac{Aw}{2}\right) F_y = F_y (w) \left(\frac{d-2Tf}{2}\right) = 1260 \times 10^3 \text{ N}$$

$$y_c = \frac{d}{2} - \frac{Tf}{2} = 190 \text{ mm}$$

$$y_w = \left(\frac{d-2Tf}{2}\right) \times \frac{1}{2} = 90 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_p = 2F_f y_{ft} + 2F_w y_{wt} = 758.8 \times 10^6 \text{ N.mm}$$

$$Z_x = \frac{M_p}{F_y} = 2168 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3$$

$$\text{shape factor } K = \frac{Z}{S} = 1.32$$

2 Buckling loads for columns

2.1 Introduction

Columns are usually considered as vertical structural elements, but they can be positioned in any orientation (e.g. diagonal and horizontal compression elements in a truss). Columns are used as major elements in trusses, building frames, and sub-structure supports for bridges (e.g. piers)[1].

- Columns support compressive loads from roofs, floors, or bridge decks.
- Columns transmit the vertical forces to the foundations and into the subsoil. The work of a column is simpler than the work of a beam.
- The loads applied to a column are only axial loads.
- Loads on columns are typically applied at the ends of the member, producing axial compressive stresses.
- However, on occasion the loads acting on a column can include axial forces, transverse forces, and bending moments (e.g. beam-columns). Columns are defined by the length between support ends.
- Short columns (e.g. footing piers).

- Long columns (e.g. bridge and freeway piers). Virtually every common construction material is used for column construction.
- Steel, timber, concrete (reinforced and pre-stressed), and masonry (brick, block, and stone). The selection of a particular material may be made based on the following.
- Strength (material) properties (e.g. steel vs. wood).
- Appearance (circular, square, or I-beam).
- Accommodate the connection of other members.
- Local production capabilities (i.e. the shape of the cross section). Columns are major structural components that significantly affect the building's overall performance and stability.
- Columns are designed with larger safety factors than other structural components.
- Failure of a joist or beam may be localized and may not severely affect the building's integrity (e.g. there is redundancy with girders and beams, but not with columns).
- Failure of a strategic column may be catastrophic for a large area of the structure.
- Failure may be due to overstressed, loss of section (deterioration), accident/sabotage (terrorism). Safety factors for columns are used to account for the following.
- Material irregularities (e.g. out of straightness).
- Support fixity at the column ends.
- Construction inaccuracies (e.g. out of plumbness).
- Workmanship.
- Unavoidable eccentric (off-axis) loading.

2.2 Short and Long Columns – Modes of Failure

Column slenderness and length greatly influence a column's ability to carry load.

- Very short, stout columns fail by crushing due to material failure.
- Failure occurs once the stress exceeds the elastic (yield point) limit of the material.
- Long, slender columns fail by buckling – a function of the column's dimensions and its modulus of elasticity.
- Buckling is the sudden uncontrolled lateral displacement of a column at which point no additional load can be supported.
- Failure occurs at a lower stress level than the column's material strength due to buckling (i.e. lateral instability).

Short columns

Short columns fail by crushing at very high stress levels that are above the elastic limit of the column material. Compressive stress for short columns is based on the basic stress equation

- If the load and column size (i.e. cross-sectional area) are known, the compressive stress may be computed [5] as

$$f_a = P_{\text{actual}} / A \leq F_a$$

where

f_a = actual compressive stress (psi or ksi)

A = cross-sectional area of the column (in²)

P_{actual} = actual load on the column (pounds or kips)

F_a = allowable compressive stress per code (psi or ksi)

- This stress equation can be rewritten into a design form to determine the required short column size when the load and allowable material strength are known.

$$A_{\text{required}} = P_{\text{actual}} / F_a$$

where

A_{required} = minimum cross-sectional area of the column

Long Columns – Euler Buckling

Long columns fail by buckling at stress levels that are below the elastic limit of the column material.

- Very short column lengths require extremely large loads to cause the member to buckle.
- Large loads result in high stresses that cause crushing rather than buckling. Buckling in long, slender columns is due to the following.
- Eccentricities in loading.
- Irregularities in the column material.

Buckling can be avoided (theoretically) if the loads were applied absolutely axially, the column material was totally homogeneous with no imperfections, and construction was true and plumb. A Swiss mathematician named Leonhard Euler (1707 – 1783) was the first to investigate the buckling behavior of slender columns within the elastic limit of the column's material.

- Euler's equation shows the relationship between the load that causes buckling of a (pinned end) column and the material and stiffness properties of the column.

The critical buckling load can be determined by the following equation.

$$P_{\text{critical}} = \pi^2 EI_{\text{min}}/L^2$$

where

P_{critical} = critical axial load that causes buckling in the column (pounds or kips)

E = modulus of elasticity of the column material (psi or ksi)

I_{min} = smallest moment of inertia of the column cross-section (in²)

(Most sections have I_x and I_y ; angles have I_x , I_y and I_z .)

L = column length between pinned ends (inches)

- As the column length increases, the critical load rapidly decreases (since it is proportional to L^2), approaching zero as a limit.
- The critical load at buckling is referred to as *Euler's critical buckling load*. Euler's equation is valid only for long, slender columns that fail due to buckling.
- Euler's equation contains no safety factors.
- Euler's equation results in compressive stresses developed in columns that are well below the elastic limit of the material.

Slenderness Ratios

The radius of gyration is a geometric property of a cross section

$$I = Ar^2 \text{ and } r = (I/A)^{1/2}$$

where

r = radius of gyration of the column cross section (in)

I = least (minimum) moment of inertia (in⁴)

A = cross-sectional area of the column (in²)

The radius of gyration is geometric property that is used in the analysis and design of columns. Using the radius of gyration, the critical stress developed in a long column at buckling can be expressed by the following equation.

$$f_{\text{critical}} = P_{\text{critical}}/A = \pi^2 EI_{\text{min}}/AL^2 = \pi^2 E(Ar^2)/AL^2 = \pi^2 E/(L/r)^2$$

The term “ L/r ” is known as the *slenderness ratio*.

- A higher slenderness ratio means a lower critical stress that will cause buckling.
- Conversely, a lower slenderness ratio results in a higher critical stress (but still within the elastic range of the material). Column sections with large R-values are more resistant to buckling.
- Compare the difference in r_{\min} values and slenderness ratios for the three column cross sections shown below.
- All three cross sections have relatively equal cross-sectional areas but very different radii of gyration about the critical buckling axis.
- All three columns are assumed to be 15 feet in length and pin-connected at both ends.

Comparison of steel cross sections with equivalent areas

The most efficient column sections for axial loads are those with almost equal r_x and r_y values.

- Circular pipe sections and square tubes are the most effective shapes since the radii of gyration about both axes are the same ($r_x = r_y$).
- Circular pipe sections and square tubes are often used as columns for light to moderate loads.

Wide-flange shapes may be preferred despite the structural advantages of closed cross-sectional shapes (like tubes and pipes).

- The practical considerations of wide-flange shapes include the following.
 - Wide-flange sections support heavy loads.
 - Wide-flange sections accommodate beam connections.

Special wide-flange sections are specifically manufactured to provide relatively symmetrical columns (r_x/r_y ratios approaching 1.0) with large load-carrying capability.

- Most of these column sections (generally W8, W10, W12, and W14) have depth and flange widths approximately equal (i.e. a “boxy” configuration).

End Support Conditions and Lateral Bracing

Previously, each column was assumed to have pinned ends in which the member ends were free to rotate (but not translate) in any direction at their ends.

- When the column buckles, it will do so in one smooth curve.
- The length of this curve is referred to as the *effective length*. In practice, a column may not be pinned at the ends.
- The column length free to buckle is greatly influenced by its end support conditions.
- The load-carrying capacity of a column is affected by the end support conditions.
- Restraining the ends of a column with a fixed support increases the load-carrying capacity of a column.
- Allowing translation as well as rotation (i.e. free end) at one end of a column generally reduces its load-carrying capacity. Column design formulas generally assume a condition in which both ends are pinned.
- When other conditions exist, the load-carrying capacity is increased or decreased, and the allowable compressive stress is increased or decreased.
- A factor K is used as a multiplier for converting the actual column length to an effective buckling length based on end conditions. The American Institute of Steel Construction (AISC) provides recommended effective length factors when ideal conditions are approximated.

Before we take this subject, we must know solution of differential equations :

$$(D - a)y \Rightarrow y = c e^{ax}$$

$$(D - b)y \Rightarrow y = c e^{-bx}$$

$$Dy = 0 \Rightarrow y = c$$

$$(D - a)(D + b)(D + c)y = 0 \Rightarrow y = c_1 e^{ax} + c_2 e^{-bx} + c_3 e^{-cx}$$

$$(D - a)(D - b)y = 0 \Rightarrow y = c_1 e^{ax} + c_2 e^{bx}$$

$$(D - a)(D - b)y = 0 \text{ where : -}$$

$$1) a = \alpha + i\beta ; b = \alpha - i\beta \quad \therefore y = e^{\alpha x}(K_1 \cos \beta x + K_2 \sin \beta x)$$

$$2) a = \alpha + \sqrt{\beta} ; b = \alpha - \sqrt{\beta} \quad \therefore y = e^{\alpha x}(K_1 \cosh \sqrt{\beta x} + K_2 \sinh \sqrt{\beta x})$$

A) columns with one end fixed and the other free

Boundary condition :

$$X = L \quad ; \quad y = 0$$

$$X = 0 \quad ; \quad dy/dx = 0$$

Taking about A point

$$M = p(a - y) = Pa - Py \quad (1)$$

Deflection equation :

$$EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = Pa - Py$$

$$EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + Py = pa$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + \frac{p}{EI}y = \frac{p}{EI}a \quad (2)$$

General solution of this equation :

$$y = A \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + a$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = A \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} + B \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} + 0$$

$$0 = B \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \rightarrow B = 0$$

$$X=0 ; y=0$$

$$0 = A + 0 + a \rightarrow A = -a$$

$$y = -a \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + a \rightarrow a \left[1 - \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \right]$$

$$X=L ; y=a$$

$$a = a \left[1 - \cos \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \right] \rightarrow 1 = \left[1 - \cos \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \right] \rightarrow \cos \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] = 0 ; \cos \frac{\pi}{2} ; \frac{3\pi}{2} ; \frac{5\pi}{2} ; = 0$$

$$L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} = \frac{\pi}{2} \rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} = \frac{\pi}{2L} \Rightarrow P = \frac{\pi^2}{4L^2} EI$$

B) Buckling load column both end fixed

Boundary conditions

1) $X=0 ; y=0$

2) $X=L ; y=0$

3) $X=0 ; dy/dx=0$

Total moment at point A = $M_0 - py$

Deflection :-

$$EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = M_0 - Py \Rightarrow EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + Py = M_0 \Rightarrow \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + \frac{Py}{EI} = \frac{M_0}{EI} \quad (1)$$

$$y = A \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{M_0}{p} \quad (2)$$

1) $X=0 ; y=0$

$$0 = A \cos 0 + B \sin 0 + \frac{M_0}{p} \rightarrow A = -M_0/p \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -A \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} + B \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} + 0$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -A\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \sin \left[x\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \cos \left[x\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \quad (4)$$

3) X = 0 ; dy/dx = 0

$$0 = B\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \quad \text{therefore B should be zero}$$

$$y = -\frac{M_0}{p} \cos \left[x\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{M_0}{p} \quad (5)$$

2) X = L ; y = 0

$$0 = -\frac{M_0}{p} \cos \left[L\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{M_0}{p} \rightarrow 0 = \frac{M_0}{p} \left[1 - \cos \left[L\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \right]$$

$$\cos \left[L\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] = 1 \quad 2\pi, 4\pi, 6\pi, \dots$$

$$L\sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} = 2\pi \rightarrow L^2 \frac{p}{EI} = 4\pi^2 \rightarrow P = \frac{4\pi^2}{L^2} EI$$

C) column with one end fixed and the other hinged

Boundary conditions

$$1) X=0 ; y=0$$

$$2) X=L ; y=0$$

$$3) X=0 ; dy/dx=0$$

$$\text{Total moment at point A} = M = H(L-X) - py$$

Deflection :-

$$EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = M \rightarrow EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} = H(L-X) - py \rightarrow EI \frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + Py = H(L-X)$$

$$\frac{d^2y}{dx^2} + \frac{Py}{EI} = \frac{H(L-X)}{EI} \quad (1)$$

The general solution :

$$y = A \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{H(L-X)}{p} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{at } x=0 ; y=0$$

$$0 = A \cos 0 + B \sin 0 + \frac{HL}{P} \rightarrow A = -\frac{HL}{P}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = -A \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} + B \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} - \frac{H}{P}$$

$$X = 0 ; \quad \frac{dy}{dx} = 0$$

$$0 = -A \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \sin 0 + B \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \cos 0 - \frac{H}{P} \rightarrow B = \frac{H}{P} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{P}}$$

$$y = A \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{H(L-X)}{p}$$

$$X=L \quad ; \quad Y=0$$

$$0 = -\frac{HL}{P} \cos \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + \frac{H}{P} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{P}} \sin \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right]$$

$$\frac{H}{P} \sqrt{\frac{EI}{P}} \sin \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] = \frac{HL}{P} \cos \left[L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \rightarrow \tan \left[\underbrace{L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}}}_{\text{angle}} \right] = \underbrace{L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}}}_{\text{radian}} \quad \text{note}(\overbrace{\tan(4.5)}^{\text{radian}}) = 4.5)$$

$$L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} = 4.5 \rightarrow \left(L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right)^2 = (4.5)^2 \rightarrow \left(L \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right)^2 = \frac{20.25}{2\pi^2}$$

$$\therefore P = \frac{2\pi^2}{L^2} EI$$

D) Both Ends Hinged

Moment in column = $-py$ (1)

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = -M$$

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + Py = 0$$

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} + \frac{p}{EI} y = 0 \quad (2)$$

The general solution :

$$y = A \cos \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] + B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{p}{EI}} \right] \quad (3)$$

Boundary conditions

1) $X=0$; $y=0$

2) $X=L$; $y=0$

$$1) X=0 ; y=0$$

$$0 = A \cos 0 + B \sin 0 \rightarrow A = 0$$

$$y = B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} \right]$$

$$2) X=L ; y=0 \quad B \neq 0 ; \sin \left[L \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} \right] = 0 = \sin \pi$$

$$0 = B \sin \left[x \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} \right] \rightarrow K = L \sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}}$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{P}{EI}} = \frac{\pi}{L} \rightarrow \frac{P}{EI} = \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} \therefore P = \frac{\pi^2}{L^2} EI$$

Example 2

Given: Two 3-1/2" standard steel pipe sections are strapped together to form a pin-connected column.

$$L = 24'$$

$$E = 29,000 \text{ ksi}$$

Find: The critical axial load when buckling occurs.

Solution

Moment of inertia for 3-1/2" standard pipe

$$I = 4.79 \text{ in}^4$$

Applicable equation: $P_{\text{critical}} = \pi^2 EI_{\text{min}} / L^2$

$$I_x = I_{\text{min}} = 2 (4.79) = 9.58 \text{ in}^4$$

$$L = 24'$$

$$P_{\text{critical}} = \pi^2 EI_{\text{min}} / L^2$$

$$= \pi^2 (29,000)(9.58) / (24 \times 12'')^2$$

$$P_{\text{critical}} = 33.1 \text{ kips}$$

Example3

Given: An 8" diameter timber pole fixed in a large concrete footing at grade and pinned at the top.

$E = 1.0 \times 10^6$ psi

Find: Maximum height of the pole to support a 25 kip load.

Solution

Applicable equation: $P_{critical} = \pi^2 EI_{min} / L^2$

• Case: One end pinned, and one end fixed.

$K = 0.7$

$L_e = 0.707 L$

$P_{critical} = \pi^2 EI_{min} / (0.707 L)^2 = 2 \pi^2 EI_{min} / L^2$

$I = \pi d^4 / 64 = \pi (8)^4 / 64 = 201.1 \text{ in}^4$

$P_{critical} = 25 \text{ kips (25,000 lb)}$

$25,000 = 2 \pi^2 (1.0 \times 10^6)(201.1 \text{ in}^4) / L^2$

$L^2 = 2 \pi^2 (1,000,000)(201.1) / 25,000 = 158,780 \text{ in}^2$

$L = 398.5'' (33.2')$

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